

Law Enforcement Against Performers of Criminal Acts of Non-Physical Sexual Harassment in Indonesia

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Abstract: Criminal acts of sexual harassment in Indonesia, both physical and non-physical, are currently continuing to increase. However, law enforcement against perpetrators of criminal acts of sexual harassment is mainly for physical sexual harassment. Forms of violence in the form of non-physical violence can include sexual comments, teasing by commenting on body shape, uttering sexual invitations, etc., which sometimes the victim feels is just a joke and is not a criminal act. This research aims to analyze legal enforcement against perpetrators of criminal acts of non-physical sexual harassment in Indonesia who are not yet fair sociological juridical approach method. The paradigm in this research is post-positivism, with secondary data sources obtained by conducting a literature study of primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. The results were analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods. Law enforcement against perpetrators of criminal acts of non-physical sexual harassment in Indonesia is still very minimal due to law enforcement officers, legal culture factors and regulatory factors, which stipulate that criminal act of physical violence are a complaint offence and not an ordinary offence. There is a lack of public attention to socialization or education carried out by the government regarding the Sexual Violence Crime Law, which is still relatively new. The lack of public attention to socialization regarding the new regulations, especially the TPKS Law, means that public awareness lacks knowledge about the applicable rules, so many people still do not understand the latest regulations in the community and the school environment.

Keywords: Law enforcement, Sexual harassment, Non-physical, Criminal.

1. Introduction

Sexual harassment is no longer an unknown event nationally but is a global event. Various platforms or media, both online and in print, have reported cases of sexual harassment. According to the World Health Organization, sexual harassment occurs in all parts of the world and is recorded almost every day. Sexual harassment, also known as sexual harassment, often happens around us, whether we are aware of it or not. Sexual harassment is a form of giving verbal, written or physical attention to a woman against her will and must be accepted "reasonably" [1].

In recent times, sexual harassment has become an issue that

has attracted public attention because the incidence of these criminal acts continues to increase. Sexual harassment can have a terrible psychological impact, especially on women, because the perpetrators of sexual harassment are known to be dominated by men. It is unfortunate that even though cases of sexual harassment often occur, society and the authorities still do not pay serious attention to it because sexual harassment is problematic to detect directly.

According to Angesti, sexual harassment is behaviour that aims to obtain sexual acts or other behaviour related to a person's sexuality by using harassment without considering the relationship or status of the victim. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), perpetrators of sexual harassment are defined as individuals who like to degrade or reduce the dignity of other people about sex or intercourse between men and women [2].

Sexual harassment does not look at social status, whether as a victim or perpetrator. Even though all parties have condemned acts of sexual harassment and harassment, these incidents do not only occur in risky places but also often occur in schools, campuses, and even in offices.

Sexual harassment is anger, humiliation, or intimidation of disturbing and undesirable sexual activity, a desire for help satisfying a party's wishes, verbal or bodily behaviour or terms with a sexual meaning, or other sexually harassing behavioural responses. Contextually appropriate actions, such as interrupting work activities, acting as if working conditions or making the situation in the work environment uncomfortable, can cause chaos due to intimidation from the perpetrator.

In the UN's view, acts of harassment against women can be defined as physical, sexual or psychological harassment that can occur within the family, such as beatings, sexual abuse of women in the household, marital rape, harmful traditional practices, and sexual exploitation. Meanwhile, things that can happen in the community, such as rape, intimidation in the workplace, places of education and other areas, trafficking in women, and forced prostitution, are carried out or permitted by the state wherever it occurs [3].

Many factors cause sexual harassment to occur. Some think

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that it happens because women are dressed in inappropriate clothes and are asked to be treated that way. This is one of the stereotypes that exist in Indonesia that women are sexual objects. This phenomenon is not only seen by the public, who think that sexual harassment is something that does not need to be exaggerated. However, the role of the government and positive law in Indonesia is still considered "light" by most people.

In Indonesia, regulations regarding non-physical sexual harassment are regulated in Law No. 12 of 2022 in Articles 4, 5 and 7. This is a way for the government to handle cases of sexual harassment that occur non-physically because, so far, Indonesia has been said to be in a legal emergency that regulates harassment carried out by non-physical means. Sexual harassment carried out by non-physical means can take the form of sexual comments, teasing by commenting on body shape, uttering sexual invitations, and even showing the victim's genitals. These actions are included in acts that have disturbed a person's human rights.

Nowadays, many cases are found that involve elements of non-physical sexual harassment, but non-physical sexual harassment is often considered normal in society, even though sexual harassment can cause trauma for the victim, fear of leaving the house, not feeling safe, and can even result in psychological disorders. A person, so special regulations are needed regarding non-physical sexual harassment. Non-physical sexual harassment can be categorized as a criminal act because there are aspects that constitute a criminal act so that it can be classified as such.

Protection for victims of sexual harassment is outlined in Law No. 12 of 2022 concerning Crimes of Sexual Violence. This law states that the witness and victim protection agency, abbreviated as LPSK, is tasked, and authorized to provide protection and other rights to witnesses and victims as regulated in the law. -Law on Witness and Victim Protection. Law no. 12 of 2022 concerning the Crime of Sexual Violence is contained in Article 65, which describes legal protection for victims by fulfilling victims' rights contained in Articles 65, 66, 67, 68, 69 and 70 [4].

In imposing criminal penalties on perpetrators of non-physical sexual harassment, it is necessary to prove whether it is true that the actions carried out by that person against other people are non-physical violations of decency, considering that it is complicated to prove the existence of non-physical sexual harassment because there is no contact. physical relationship between the perpetrator and the recipient of the harassment, so the presence of witnesses at the time of the incident is an essential key to proving that there was sexual harassment against the victim. Currently, sexual harassment is regulated in Law No. 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence. Still, this law does not yet clearly regulate the limitations that constitute non-physical sexual harassment. Regarding these limitations, there is still debate about which acts are included in non-physical sexual harassment or not. Based on the description above, we will examine how the law is enforced against criminal acts of non-physical sexual harassment in Indonesia [5].

2. Research Methods

In this research, the author uses a post-positivism paradigm, which states that legal science does not only deal with statutory regulations. Law must be applied, and it is more likely not to question the value of justice and its usefulness to society.

The approach method in this research is normative juridical, namely, research sourced from secondary data by conducting literature studies on primary legal materials in the form of laws and regulations related to sexual harassment, secondary legal materials in the form of books, and research results. Scientific works such as journals that contain primary and tertiary legal materials in legal dictionaries and encyclopedias. The data obtained was then analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods.

3. Research Results and Discussion

A. Non-Physical Sexual Harassment

The above section says how to prepare a subsection. Just copy and paste the subsection, whenever you need it. The numbers will be automatically changes when you add new subsection. Once you paste it, change the subsection heading as per your requirement [6].

Article 1 point 1 of Law Number 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Harassment provides the understanding that "Criminal Acts of Sexual Harassment are all acts that fulfil the elements of criminal acts as regulated in this law and other acts of sexual harassment as regulated in the law. Law to the extent specified in this law." What is stated in Article 1 number 1 of Law Number 12 of 2022 is not a definition of the Crime of Sexual Harassment, but rather the "limits of understanding" of the term Crime of Sexual Harassment if that term is used in Law Number 12 of 2022. Article 1 number 1 of Law Number 12 of 2022 defines that if the term Sexual Harassment Crime is used in this law, then it means:

- a. All acts that fulfill the elements of a criminal act as regulated in this law
- b. Other acts of sexual harassment are regulated in the law to the extent specified in this law.

The existence of two groups (types) of qualifications for the Crime of Sexual Harassment is regulated in more detail in Article 4 of Law Number 12 of 2022, where one of the Crimes of Sexual Harassment is what Article 4 paragraph (1) letter a refers to as "harassment non-physical sexual". This non-physical sexual harassment, because it is regulated in Article 4 paragraph (1), means that it is a criminal act of sexual violence, which is regulated in Law Number 12 of 2022 as a new criminal act [7].

The formulation of criminal acts and criminal threats relating to non-physical sexual harassment is regulated in Article 5, which stipulates that "Every person who commits non-physical sexual acts aimed at the body, sexual desire and reproductive organs to degrade a person's dignity based on sexuality. And his decency shall be punished for non-physical sexual harassment, with a maximum imprisonment of 9 (nine) months and a maximum fine of IDR 10,000,000.00 (ten million rupiah)." In the article-by-article explanation of Article 5, it is stated that

"what is meant by "non-physical sexual acts are statements, gestures or activities that are inappropriate and lead to sexuality with the aim of humiliating or humiliating".

Article 5 has given a name (qualification) to the criminal act formulated in Article 5 as "non-physical sexual harassment". There is no information in Law Number 12 of 2022 regarding this term. However, from an everyday language perspective, this term can be explained using the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI). Harassment is a process, act, or way of harassing where the word to harass means to despise (worthless), humiliate, ignoring", so harassment can be interpreted as an act of looking down on (useless), humiliating, ignore. The word "sexual" indicates that the harassment is related to sexual matters, and the word "non-physical" suggests that sexual harassment is carried out without physical contact or touching of body parts between the person harassing and the person being harassed [8].

In Indonesia, regulations regarding non-physical sexual harassment have just been regulated and ratified in Law No. 12 of 2022 in Articles 4, 5 and 7. This is a way for the government to handle cases of sexual harassment that occur non-physically because, so far, Indonesia is said to be in a legal emergency that regulates harassment carried out by non-physical means. Sexual harassment carried out by non-physical means can take the form of sexual comments, teasing by commenting on body shape, uttering sexual invitations, and even showing the victim's genitals. These actions are included in acts that have disturbed a person's human rights. Currently, many cases are found that involve elements of non-physical sexual harassment in them. However, non-physical sexual harassment is often considered normal in society, even though sexual harassment can cause trauma for the victim. Afraid to leave the house not feeling safe can even result in psychological disturbance to a person, so special arrangements are needed regarding non-physical sexual harassment. Non-physical sexual harassment can be categorized as a criminal act because there are aspects that constitute a criminal act, so it can be classified as such.

According to Articles 289 to 269 of the Criminal Code (Criminal Code), there are only two types of sexual violence that are recognized by law, namely rape and sexual immorality. Nowadays, the types of sexual harassment cases are increasing along with the times, for example, cases of sexual harassment that occur non-physically. Before the ratification of Law no. 12 of 2022 concerning Crimes of Sexual Violence, often the ITE Law was used as a diversion to deal with cases of harassment that occur non-physically, such as the fetish case, which has recently been widely discussed, the perpetrator is charged with Articles of violation of the ITE Law which include internet actions and information which includes threats of violence or intimidation, on the other hand, non-physical sexual harassment cannot be punished because no law regulates it. Unwanted sexual activity makes victims, especially women, feel embarrassed, intimidated, and humiliated [9].

When taken one by one, Article 281 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code can be used for sexual harassment, namely that decency is violated when someone acts against their wishes. However, this clause prioritizes violations of decency rather

than attacks on the victim's body and dignity, whereas if we look at the definition of pornography contained in Article 1 point 1 of Law Number. 44 of 2008 concerning pornography, which states "Pornography is an image, sketch, illustration, photo, writing, voice, sound, moving image, animation, cartoon, conversation, body movement, or other forms of message through various forms of communication media and performances in public, which contains obscenity or sexual exploitation which violates the norms of decency in society", Articles 8, 9, 34 and 35 of the Pornography Law can be used as a legal basis for non-physical sexual harassment, although the application of the above articles is not enough to guarantee clarity the law at that time. Non-physical sexual harassment requires its own set of standards to be regulated.

Before the enactment of Law No. 12 of 2022 concerning Criminal Acts of Sexual Violence, which contains regulations regarding physical and non-physical harassment in Articles 4, 5, 6 and 7, there was no formal definition of sexual harassment in the law. However, the Criminal Code only regulates criminal acts of violations of Article 281 paragraph 1 and obscenity (Articles 290,292, 293, 294, and 296). At that time, the Draft Law on the Elimination of Sexual Violence (2017) tried to fill the legal gap in the Criminal Code regarding non-physical sexual harassment by defining sexual harassment: "sexual violence committed in the form of physical or non-physical acts against another person, which is related to body parts. A person and related sexual desires, resulting in other people being intimidated, humiliated, humiliated or humiliated," which has now been ratified with Law no. 12 of 2022 concerning the Crime of Sexual Violence, the passing of this law was carried out to provide a sense of security to the public when in public places, especially in the infrastructure sector, the government's obligation to ensure a safe and comfortable environment and public facilities, as well as an integrated security system in areas and public open spaces. However, in the law, there are still vague norms where the law does not regulate the boundaries of what constitutes an act of non-physical sexual harassment [10].

In imposing criminal penalties on perpetrators of non-physical sexual harassment, it is necessary to prove whether it is true that the actions carried out by that person against other people are non-physical violations of decency, considering that it is tough to prove the existence of non-physical sexual harassment because there is no contact. physical relationship between the perpetrator and the recipient of the harassment, so the presence of witnesses at the time of the incident is an essential key to proving that there was sexual harassment against the victim. Currently, sexual harassment is regulated in Law No. 12 of 2022 concerning the Crime of Sexual Violence. However, this law does not yet clearly regulate the limitations that constitute non-physical sexual harassment. Regarding these limitations, there is still debate about which acts are included in non-physical sexual harassment or not.

Article 5 of the TPKS Law contains elements of regulation regarding non-physical sexual violence, which can be used as a basis for ensnaring perpetrators. However, in my opinion, in the aspects of this article, there are still weaknesses in the elements of non-physical sexual acts, the explanation of which is not

found in the body of this law. Apart from that, the aspect of sexuality and morality also does not have an explanation in this law, where morality also has a broad scope regarding criminal acts of morality. Apart from that, regarding the explanation of the elements of non-physical sexual acts which are not found in the body of the law. This TPKS. So, this can be used for interpretation according to the law, which, if the meaning sought is not there, requires looking for an interpretation in the explanation of the law because all laws have an explanation of the article. If we look at the interpretation according to the explanation of the law, what is meant by "non-physical acts are statements, gestures or activities that are inappropriate and lead to sexuality with the aim of humiliating or humiliating [11].

B. Law Enforcement against Non-Physical Sexual Harassment

Komnas Perempuan's complaint data throughout 2022 shows sexual violence as the dominant form of violence against women (2,228 cases/38.21%), followed by psychological violence (2,083 cases/35.72%). Meanwhile, data from service institutions is dominated by physical violence (6,001 cases/38.8%), followed by sexual violence (4,102 cases/26.52%). Let us look at the data on complaints to the National Commission on Violence Against Women in the public domain. Sexual violence is always the highest (1,127 cases), while in the personal sphere, the highest is psychological violence (1,494). In contrast to service institutions, data for 2022 shows that most of the public and personal spheres are physical [12].

The sexual violence data shows that cases of sexual violence that often occur are only in physical form, such as sexual intercourse, rape and molestation. Meanwhile, cases of non-physical sexual violence do not yet exist, even though Article 5 of the TPKS Law stipulates that non-physical sexual violence is a criminal act. One of the things that makes this case of non-physical sexual violence not yet exist is that some people do not understand that things they often or usually do, such as saying pornographic sentences, are prohibited and can be reported to the authorities. Apart from that, several things make cases of sexual violence that have not yet been followed up. More specifically, the author describes the things that cause instances of sexual violence not to be followed up:

1) Law enforcement

Law enforcement, especially the police, in determining and detaining a suspect in connection with a crime of non-physical sexual harassment must be based on the provisions of Article 1 point 14 of Law no. 8 of 1981 concerning Civil Procedure Law (Criminal Code), which reads: "A suspect is a person who, because of his actions or circumstances, based on preliminary evidence is reasonably suspected of being the perpetrator of a criminal act" and Article 17 of the Criminal Code which reads "An arrest order is issued against a person who is strongly suspected of committing criminal offence based on sufficient preliminary evidence." In obtaining preliminary evidence, investigators must fulfil material and formal requirements.

Non-physical sexual harassment that occurs is often unknown to other people because the mechanism for

complaints to the police by victims of sexual violence is rarely implemented, where most women are only aware then report it to the police. Many victims are embarrassed and just keep quiet without rebelling because they feel that what has happened is a disgrace to them. Furthermore, only a few people take legal actions[13].

One of the obstacles experienced in law enforcement of criminal acts of non-physical sexual violence is the process of proof, where this non-physical sexual violence usually occurs in public places such as bus stops, on roads and sidewalks, so that law enforcers experience difficulties if the victim experienced non-physical sexual harassment in a place like that. Still, there were no tools to support the proof process, such as CCTV recordings or other soundproofing devices.

Evidence of crime is significant for uncovering a criminal act in law enforcement. The evidence covers comprehensive matters. Evidence includes everything related to the evidence itself, from collecting evidence, presenting it to the court, and evaluating each piece of evidence to the burden of proof in court. In non-criminal cases of non-physical sexual harassment, proof is one of the obstacles experienced in law enforcement.

The proof is difficult to prove because this non-physical sexual harassment takes the form of verbal, visual and also verbal-visual, so when the perpetrator does this, the perpetrator initially only intended to tease, turning into holding a gun to get pleasure or get pleasure from feeling disturbed by the victim, so that if the victim feels disturbed by the perpetrator's actions, this is an example of a case of non-physical sexual harassment. Still, suppose the perpetrator regrets this, and there are no witnesses other than the victim or anything that can prove as an example that the perpetrator is indeed catcalling. In that case, it will be challenging to establish the perpetrator's actions.

In crimes of non-physical sexual harassment, the evidence submitted by the victim, which is then formulated/assessed by investigators, is vulnerable. The legal argument is if, for example, the perpetrator said to the victim, "Let's kiss," then who was watching at that time? Fortunately, witnesses can hear with the help of CCTV or cellphone cameras. If not, the reporting victim's report will inevitably be in vain and only present a statement to investigators that seems baseless even though the incident is actual, then, if there is a case where the perpetrator peeks at someone taking a shower. What if this happens in remote areas without CCTV or cell phone access? Because the victim's confession cannot be used as a basis for ensnaring the perpetrator even if the incident is actual. Herein lies the weakness of proof of non-physical sexual crimes. However, this does not mean that the author concludes that victims should not report if they experience non-physical sexual harassment. However, before making a report, you must consider the legal aspects of Article 184, paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code and other statutory provisions. Because if not, there is potential for a report back that will create new problems [14].

2) The public does not understand the rules regarding non-physical sexual violence

The public's understanding of the rules regarding non-physical sexual violence is very minimal, so when cases of

sexual violence occur, they only assume that these acts are just everyday things that happen and do not take them too seriously. This causes cases of sexual violence to go unreported. Apart from that, because the TPKS Law is still relatively new, people do not understand the rules regarding non-physical sexual violence. Even though many people think that this is trivial behaviour, it is not a polite thing to do. In this case, the victim also feels uncomfortable and may even believe that they are being harassed and humiliated, as if they can easily be used as a matter of morality, even though not directly, so that this act cannot be considered trivial.

3) There are no reports from victims of non-physical sexual violence

The role of the victim in conveying the case he is experiencing is vital because non-physical sexual violence is a complaint offence which can be processed if the victim reports it to the authorities. Victims of criminal acts of non-physical sexual violence have the right to report the crime they committed, naturally, to the authorities, such as the police or investigators. Reporting criminal acts of non-physical sexual violence is an essential first step in the process of law enforcement and prosecuting perpetrators of criminal acts of non-physical sexual violence. Still many cases of criminal acts of non-physical sexual violence often occur continuously because the victims are those who experience it and do not know that it is a criminal offence, so they do not report it to the authorities. Victims are more vulnerable to remaining silent rather than talking about an event that makes them embarrassed, and they do not want what they experienced to be known to the public, including friends and family.

In cases of non-physical sexual harassment, when the victim feels embarrassed or does not dare to report it to the authorities, it is the family who must accompany or replace the victim. Still, most of the victim's families do not care or pay attention to this because this non-physical sexual violence is ordinary things or trivial things for them [15].

Most victims' families have minimal knowledge about the applicable rules, so when a family member experiences non-physical sexual violence, they do not take it too seriously. So, many cases of non-physical sexual violence occur but are not followed up because the family is not supportive.

Then, there is a lack of public attention to the government's socialization or education regarding the TPKS Law, which is still relatively new. The lack of public attention to socialization regarding new regulations, especially the TPKS Law, has resulted in minimal public awareness of the applicable rules, so both in the community and in the school environment, there are still many people who do not understand the new regulations, especially for They have always considered the crime of non-physical sexual harassment to be just a joke, so this crime continues to occur. This proves that the public still lacks knowledge about the legal regulations that prohibit people from hooting at people because the public considers that non-physical sexual violence is just a joke and believes that there are no binding regulations that will be sanctioned when violated.

Many things make people out there still commit criminal acts

of non-physical sexual violence, even though there is a law that regulates this matter and socialization, or legal counselling has been carried out. But if this has become a habit, it is difficult to stop it. Apart from chronic factors, there are other factors that make this continue to happen, namely environmental, educational, and gender inequality factors.

Community behaviour also influences the law enforcement of criminal acts, especially non-physical sexual violence. In various cases of non-physical sexual violence that occurs in the community, it occurs due to underlying factors, for example, a lack of public awareness, getting pleasure, or just for fun. Just.

Lack of legal awareness and public obedience to the law will make it difficult to enforce it. This continues with the government's lack of socialisation regarding new regulations, which can also cause the public to lack awareness of things they should not do.

Despite the positive developments of the TPKS Law, there are still several challenges to enforcing it. Because the public still considers non-physical sexual harassment to be a regular act, law enforcement officials such as the police do not yet understand what catcalling is. Apart from that, there is also a culture of blaming the victim, so in the end, it places a burden on the victim, and the victim does not report it to law enforcement officials. On average, victims of non-physical sexual harassment will feel uncomfortable, annoyed, embarrassed, and even afraid [15].

4) The crime of non-physical sexual violence is a complaint offense

This criminal act of non-physical sexual violence, which is a complaint offense, means that many cases of non-physical sexual violence are not followed up because the victims do not know about this and so do not report it to the authorities, which results in this non-physical sexual violence not proceeding to the investigation or prosecution stage. This non-physical sexual violence has long been a habit for some people. The habits referred to here are things such as wolf-whistling at people in public places, commenting on someone's intimate forms or saying sexual sentences, even movements that contain sexual elements are often done by people without knowing that the actions they take can have negative effects. to the victim, such as the emergence of emotional problems in the victim and even trauma that can affect the victim's social life. Apart from that, based on Article 7 of the TPKS Law, non-physical sexual violence is a complaint offense that can be processed if the injured party (victim) reports it to the authorities. Therefore, it is very important to conduct socialization regarding the TPKS Law to the wider community regarding things that have become customary to reduce and provide knowledge to the public so that cases of non-physical sexual violence can be followed up by law enforcers if there are cases that occur [2].

Verbal sexual harassment against women is also considered not to reflect the values contained in the foundation of the Indonesian state itself, namely Pancasila. This is due to injustice towards women who are verbally harassed (catcalling) and do not receive justice as stated in the fifth principle, namely social justice, for all Indonesian people. In general, women are often the objects of sexual harassment, and men are the perpetrators.

However, there is nothing that can cover the possibility that men could become objects of sexual harassment by perpetrators of women or even members of the same sex. Victims of sexual harassment themselves tend to be afraid to report it; this tends to be due to a lack of evidence, and if the victim dares to report it, it is not uncommon for the victim's report to not be processed by law enforcement, lack of knowledge of law enforcers regarding criminal acts of non-physical sexual harassment is one of the factors. If the victim's report is not processed, it will undoubtedly cause injustice to the victim for the crime he received [16].

4. Conclusion

- 1) Law enforcement against perpetrators of criminal acts of non-physical sexual harassment in Indonesia is still very minimal due to law enforcement officers, legal culture factors and regulatory factors, which stipulate that criminal act of physical violence are a complaint offense and not an ordinary offense. There is a lack of public attention to socialization or education carried out by the government regarding the Sexual Violence Crime Law, which is still relatively new. The lack of public attention to socialization regarding new regulations, especially the TPKS Law, means that public awareness lacks knowledge about the applicable rules. In the community and school environment, many people still do not understand the new regulations.
- 2) It is necessary to reconstruct the regulations on the Criminal Act of Sexual Violence to change it from a complaint offense to an ordinary offense, and there needs to be synergy between law enforcement officials and the community so that victims of criminal acts of sexual harassment are willing to report their cases so that there is protection for the victims.

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